

Psychological experience of Covid-19 patients during quarantine: A qualitative study

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ABSTRACT: The ongoing restrictive measures and emotional suffering related to COVID-19 pandemic have potentially led thousands of people to experience a decrease in socio-economic status as well as increased levels of psychological stress. The objective of the study was to explore the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients regarding the quarantine period. Qualitative exploratory phenomenological approach was used, Data was collected from confirmed case of COVID-19 who were quarantined and fulfill the inclusion and exclusion criteria by using semi-structured interview guide. The in-depth interviews were conducted face to face. These in-depth interviews were recorded and were further transcribed and then analyzed by using thematic analysis. Qualitative analysis of the interview findings was categorized into six overarching themes. Mainly these themes were, 1) First response to the COVID-19 disease among the participants, 2) Development of unpleasant emotions among the quarantined COVID-19 patients, 3) Experience of Fear and stress among them, 4) Death Anxiety among the participants due to high mortality rates from corona disease, 5) Perceptions of Social and Psychological support which helped them in successful recovery and stability, and 6) Post discharge concerns and Problems which they are going to face after moving homes from the hospital. In conclusion it was found that patients' psychological experiences during the COVID-19 crisis were complicated, involving COVID-19-related mental distress symptoms, expectations for their post-discharge lives, and attempts to make sense of their experiences.

Keywords: Covid-19, Quarantine, Psychological Experience, Anxiety.

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1. Introduction

The World Health Organization has named COVID-19 as the sixth public health emergency of global significance (WHO). The COVID-19 epidemic has endangered people's lives and health (Qiu et al., 2020). Coronavirus infection has resulted in severe morbidity and mortality in people all over the world (Rashed and Eissa, 2020). COVID-19 patients have mild to severe respiratory and non-respiratory symptoms (Huang et al., 2020). The (COVID-19) pandemic is a global health emergency as a result. The disease is very contagious and has a high fatality rate in some populations, especially the elderly and those with concomitant conditions (Kluge, 2020).

The symptoms of a viral infection can range from minor to severe. Fatigue, fever, coughing, and trouble breathing are all symptoms of the virus. These patients require isolation due to the high risk of illness transmission, which may cause significant emotional suffering (Wang et al., 2020b). The COVID-19 pandemic, like the SARS and MERS pandemics, has left many patients in serious bodily and psychological distress even after they have been discharged (Park et al., 2020).

On February 26, 2020, Karachi, Sindh province, saw the confirmation of Pakistan's first COVID-19 case (Waris et al., 2020). Pakistan faced a critical situation and strict measures were needed to be taken to avert the threat of a national health crisis (Khan et al., 2020). As of September 28, 2020, Pakistan had 311,516 confirmed cases overall and 6,474 fatalities. Among all the provinces, Sindh reported the most confirmed cases (136,395). Punjab was second with 99,292 confirmed cases, while Islamabad had 16,532 confirmed cases. Pakistan ranks 14th globally in terms of the overall number of confirmed cases (Rehman et al., 2020).

In response to this global health emergency, federal and international health organizations implemented quarantine and lockdown procedures to contain the virus' spread. Flight cancellations, avoiding large crowds, using face masks under duress in many nations, social exclusion, telecommuting, homeschooling kids, and health advisories to stay at home were some of the other methods (Bedford et al., 2020). A public health emergency of this magnitude has far-reaching effects on human health and well-being as well as psychological distress and symptoms such as stress, fear, and concern in the general population, despite the WHO and international health authorities' best efforts to contain the epidemic (Wang et al., 2020a).

Quarantine facilities were set up in various parts of Pakistan in response to this crisis. As further public health measures to prevent COVID-19, the government constructed isolation wards and quarantine zones in teaching hospitals (Saqlain et al., 2020) (Hossain et al., 2020). According to WHO recommendations, anyone who have COVID-19 that has been confirmed in a test should be isolated for 14 days after their last contact with the patient (WHO).

In order to determine if individuals who may have been exposed to an infectious disease become ill and reduce the risk of spreading the illness to others, quarantine involves isolating and restricting their mobility. For those who go through it, quarantine is frequently an unpleasant experience. Dramatic impacts can result from being cut off from loved ones, losing one's independence, not knowing how serious a sickness is, and being bored (Brooks et al., 2020a).

Moreover, the ongoing preventive measures and emotional distress related to COVID- 19 pandemic might potentially lead thousands of people to experience a decrease

in socio- economic status as well as augmented levels of psychological stress (Garcovich et al., 2020). Though all humans are at jeopardy of psychological harm when kept in quarantine, the most susceptible in these situations are children and adolescents, older adults, minority groups, those from lower socio- economic groups, females and people with pre- existing psychological health conditions. (Usher et al., 2020).

Isolation poses more serious issues for those who already have mental health conditions and can worsen angst and worry. Moreover, mental health results are worse the longer a person spends in quarantine, which may mean that confinement itself might be viewed and experienced as a traumatic event (Usher et al., 2020).

During an epidemic or pandemic, quarantine, preventative, and control efforts may result in insufficient or missing psychosocial interventions by patients and medical personnel (Lima et al., 2020). Studies show that among COVID-19 survivors, tension, depression, worry, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are all very frequent. Four physical symptoms are present in 33.4 percent of COVID-19 survivors who are under psychological stress, with headache accounting for 32.3 percent of cases (Hao et al., 2020).

2. Theoretical Framework

Bio-psychosocial Model in the COVID-19

The source, appearance, and outcome of health and illness are determined by interactions among the biological, psychological, and social elements, according to George L. Engel. According to bio-psychosocial paradigm, several factors interact to affect a person's health-related results, including their genetic make-up (biology), psychological health, and behavior (psychology), as well as their social and cultural milieu (Morrison and Bennett, 2009).

The bio-psychological and social processes are ideally suited for the BPS framework to explain or investigate the experiences of COVID-19 patients while they are under quarantine. It offers a graphic representation of this model for the COVID-19's experiences during the quarantine period.

Biological Influence on Health

The biological aspect of health focuses on physiological concerns, taking into account symptoms, diagnosis, and preventative medical measures. It is significant to understand that some physiological changes in may resemble COVID-19 illness symptoms (e.g. fever. cough, shortness of breath) (Diamond et al., 2020).

Psychology Influence on Health

The bio-psychosocial model's psychological factor looks for a psychological explanation for a specific symptom or set of symptoms (e.g., impulsivity, irritability, overwhelming sadness, etc.) (Diamond et al., 2020).

The thoughts, feelings, and actions that are normally taken into account when evaluating mental health are included in the psychological domain of health. During the COVID-19 pandemic, as Slade et al. (2009) noted, there may be an understandable psychological crisis as this is a period of increased ambiguity and worry, depression, and difficulty accessing mental health treatments.

Social Influence on Health

Socioeconomic position, culture, and religion are examples of social influences. For instance, one may be more susceptible to stress and disease if they lose their work or break a relationship. Such life experiences may make someone more susceptible to depression, which may then lead to physical health issues.

The connections and surroundings of an individual are taken into account in the social domain of health, which is severely constrained for everyone owing to the hazards associated with COVID-19 and especially for populations that are exposed to it. This area takes into account factors including the quality of family connections, the usage and effectiveness of social support, the interactions between patients and healthcare providers, and social factors of health (e.g. Access and quality of necessary resources, education, and employment). Social distancing rules are a major guideline when it comes to the experiences of COVID-19 patients during quarantine. These rules are important since they address psychological issues. According to research, social isolation (i.e., a lack of contacts with others or the larger society) and solitude (i.e., a sense of being alone or lacking a social network) are significantly linked to worse mental health consequences, such as hopelessness (Leigh-Hunt et al. 2017). Relationships between patients and providers have changed, as well as people's capacity to interact socially with crucial support networks (Gildner and Thayer 2020).

3. Significance of the Study

The COVID-19 phase is regarded as a critical and painful time in the lives of patients. Patients experience significant stress throughout this crisis in addition to their physical illness since acute infectious outbreaks have a detrimental impact on their psychological health.

Patients with epidemic diseases are more likely than other patients to encounter psychological problems during outbreaks, and they may face stress disorders, fear, anxiety, and long-term psychological health issues to varied degrees (Moradi et al., 2020).

This study may be able to solve the difficulties experienced by COVID-19 patients by examining their psychological experiences during quarantine.

4. Research Objective

To explore the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during the quarantine period.

5. Materials and Methods

This study was conducted using a qualitative exploratory phenomenological study approach, which allowed for a thorough analysis of the phenomena. The COVID-19 isolation wards served as the locations for patient recruitment and data collecting interviews. The included hospitals were Mayo Hospital Lahore, Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore, Jinnah Hospital Lahore and Government Mozang Teaching Hospital Lahore. The duration of this study was from May 2021 to October 2021.

The purposive sampling technique was used to recruit the COVID-19 Survivors for the study. Enrollment of participants to sample was continued till attainment of saturation point where no new themes identified. Saturation occurred on 13 sample size. The inclusion criteria were as under:

- Patients Tested Positive for COVID-19 through Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR) and experienced complete hospital quarantine and tested negative.
- Age 40-70
- Both male/Female

The exclusion criteria were as under:

- Health professionals
- Person who is still exhibiting any signs of COVID-19 infection

- Individuals' who is previously diagnosed with any mental disorder.
- COVID patients who are/were on ventilator.
- Patients that may unable to communicate effectively.

An interview guide was created as a tool for gathering data. The original researcher created the interview guide using her own experience, in-depth literature searches, and expert evaluation. The first section of the interview covered demographic information on the patient's characteristics, such as name, age, and marital status, level of education, economic situation, and social standing at the time of quarantine. The second section of the survey was made up of questions that focused on the psychological experiences of COVID-19 patients while they were under quarantine. The information was open for further investigation and exploration by the researcher. A formal informed consent was obtained from research participants. Throughout the data gathering procedure, all ethical issues were taken into account. Participants' information was gathered wherever they felt comfortable. The participants were scheduled for an in-depth interview. Face-to-face in-depth interviews were done using open-ended questions in accordance with the interview guide. Free speech was welcomed among the participants.

As it was convenient for the participants, the interviews were taped using an audio recorder on a cell phone. Next, after full transcription of the recorded recordings, each participant's name was given a unique identity. By creating categories and themes from the data, the analysis of the data was completed. After the initial interview, analysis was begun so that recurrent topics could be investigated. Thematic analysis framework approach was used to examine and describe the findings of qualitative data.

Regarding the ethical consideration, an approval to conduct the study was taken from the ethical review committee of University of Health Sciences, Lahore. Ethical considerations were followed according to the ethical principles of Helsinki declaration. The privacy and consent of the participants was taken care. Further, any harm to the participant was evaded.

6. Findings

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variables	No of Participants	Percentage
Gender		
Male	09	75%
Female	03	25%
Age		
41-50 years	07	58.3%
>50 years	05	41.7%
Marital status		
Married	10	83.3%
Unmarried	02	16.7%
Education Level		
Uneducated	03	25%
High School	05	41.7%
>High School	04	33.3%
Days in Hospital		
6-10 Days	02	16.7%
> 10 Days	10	83.3%
Monthly Income		
≤30,000 PKR	4	33.3%
>30,000 PKR	8	66.7%

Among the participants 9 (75%) were male and 3 (25%) were female. The age of study participants ranges 40 years and above where 7 (58.3%) were age 40 to 50 years and remaining 5(41.7%) were above 50 years of age. Majority of the participants (10/12) were married and 5 were educated up to high school while 4 were above high school education. Hospital stay of majority (10/12) participants was more than 10 days. 4 out of 12 study participants were having monthly income <30,000 PKR and remaining 8 were having monthly income above 30,000 PKR.

Table 2. Themes and Subthemes emerged from the interviews findings

Theme	Subthemes
First response to the disease	Negation of the disease Mixing COVID-19 for other illnesses
Development of unpleasant emotions	Loneliness and the absence of friends Hopelessness Uncertainty and confusion Experience of Anxiety and stress Anxiety of death Worries about family members
Experience of Fear & stress	Fear of Relapse Fear of Hospital environment
Death Anxiety	Fear of Death Fear to See peoples are dying Scared to leave the family alone.
Perceptions of Social and Psychological support	Emotional support of a family. Psychological support from medical staff. Religious beliefs Patients' good essence
Post discharge concerns and Problems	Concerns about one's job Stigmatization of people Difficulty adhering to quarantine standards. Perceptions and acceptance of people's behavior and attitude.

Theme 1: First response to the disease

The participants' First response to the disease was the first theme that was identified from participants' comments. Two subthemes made up this theme were: Negation of the disease and Mixing COVID-19 for other illnesses.

Sub-theme 1.1: Negation of the disease

All patients expressed by denial when presenting clinical symptoms such as cough with fever and breathing difficulty. One participant stated that,

"Definitely not, how could it be such an incidence? It might be a cold" (ID4).

Sub-theme 1.2: Mixing COVID-19 for other illnesses

Majority of the participants initially mixed COVID-19 with other respiratory diseases like asthma etc. One of the study participants' said,

"I started out with a sore throat. Due to the fragrance of these drugs hurts my throat and increase the frequency of my painful throats, I assumed that their use and alcohol were to blame. Therefore, I did not, take it seriously at all. I was really cautious as well; therefore I found it hard to accept that I had the corona illness" (ID6).

Theme 2: Development of unpleasant emotions

Numerous unpleasant emotional triggers were recorded, where Emotional reactions to the disease at various stages and Extreme focus on their symptoms were the most notable features among the study participants.

Sub-theme 2.1: Social Isolation and the absence of friends

The absence of a companion or family members upon arrival to the ward was one of the key issues mentioned by the participants. For example, one of the participants said, *"When I was quarantined, even my children were forbidden from meeting me due to fear of transmission. I am alone for entire weeks, and no one can come to see me. I was quite troubled by that"* (ID1).

All the participants expressed that their family members were their spiritual supports and their absence during their stay in quarantine is very upsetting for them.

"I was in such bad conditions that I could hardly move." I felt as like my world was crashing around me, and there was no one familiar to assist me" (ID4).

Sub-theme 2.2: Hopelessness

Majority of the participants were feeling hopeless upon arrival while they were just attempting to accept and believe their illness as COVID-19 patients. One participant stated that,

"I believed this was the end of my life and there was no hope for me and that was the breaking point" (ID7).

One other participant stated that

"I had a lot of negative ideas in my mind. I stopped wanting to live" (ID6).

Sub-theme 2.3: Uncertainty and confusion

Majority of the participants told that a sense of uncertainty increasing from the anxiety and stress of diagnosis with the disease and management of COVID-19. As a participant stated that,

"I am very much worried and asking to the doctors about my diagnosis and I get the same response all the time "you will be expressed when the test results come out". I know this uncertain nature of the disease make me worried, but I cannot control it" (ID8).

Even the treatment is not very clear as said by one of the participants

"Nurses and doctors would come and give me an injection of serum every day. Every doctor tries to test a new drug on us. But no one knows what will happen" (ID12).

Sub-theme 2.4: Experience of Anxiety and stress

The main concerns of the majority of study participants was anxiety and stress of death and dependence. One participant, for instance, said,

"I was always frightened I might die, especially while I was in the hospital and had acute shortness of breath" (ID11).

Another participant stated that,

"I was much more afraid when I was in the quarantine center since I could see the people on the other beds" (ID10).

Theme 3: Experience of Fear and Stress

One other chief theme take out from the participants' interviews were their experience of fear and stress, which was found very common between the participants due to the novelty and strange nature of Corona virus disease.

Sub-theme 3.1: Fear of Relapse

Majority of the participants were afraid of the nature of disease that in many cases the disease reoccurs after the patients were fully recovered. One participant stated that, *"I couldn't sleep, due to anxiety as I was scared of dying without being able to cohere on to the hands of my family, depression overcame me. This feeling is due to the unpredictable nature of the disease"* (ID9).

Sub-theme 3.2: Fear of Hospital environment

The high number of COVID-19 patients was having fear of crowded hospitals environment. Some participants considered hospital as terrifying place as stated by one of the participants,

"Due to such a huge crowd in the hospital, I was worried that my sickness would go undiagnosed and untreated" (ID6).

Where one participant stated that,

"Because of the large number of patients, I was continually concerned that I would be treated unfairly and that the nurses and physicians would neglect me" (ID11).

Theme 4: Death Anxieties:

Participants were having fear of death unexpectedly. They were thinking of death as an unpleasant and unforeseen event.

Sub-theme 4.1: Fear of self-Death

One of the key topics take out from the interviews was fear and terror of death subtheme. Stated by one of the participants,

"I think I'm done; because pneumonia caused by the new coronavirus is diagnosed to me. My body is trembling because I am so terrified" (ID8).

Moreover the vast majority of participants had a dread of dying as evidenced by the statement of one of the participants,

"Death is the first thing that comes to my mind. I feel like I cannot live anymore. I am too much afraid of death" (ID9).

Sub-theme 4.2: Fear to see peoples are dying

COVID-19 is a kind of disease which killed a large number of patients in a very short time. One participant stated that,

"I witnessed my own death a number of times by observing other patients dying. I believed that death was just around the corner to me. I had a constant fear of dying horribly. At the time, I wanted to go quietly" (ID2).

Another participant replied as response to a question that,

"I was really afraid of dying in this way after witnessing the deaths of other patients. I'm young, and I do not want to die under these ruthless circumstances and at such a young age" (ID6).

Sub-theme 4.3: Fear of leaving their families alone

Some patients stated worries about the health and life of their families and relatives because of a history of close contact. One participant mentioned in interview that, *"My family has been isolated because of me; I am anxious that they are septic by me. I am worried that about their health"* (ID2).

Stated by one participant,

"I believe that I truly am a stirrer and I feel responsible for problems of my family. My family members need isolation under medical monitoring just because of my disease". (ID1).

Theme 5: Perceptions of Social and Psychological support

Following four subthemes were extracted from the participants' interviews

Sub-theme 5.1: Emotional support of my Family

All patients acknowledged that their loved ones served as their spiritual foundations while they were in the hospital. The term "family emotional support" describes how an individual perceives the family members' availability, sufficiency, and quality of assistance during times of COVID-19 crisis.

One of the participants' replied as response to interview that,

"I am not sure whether I would have lived if my family members had not supported me. Most of the time I spoke to them and heard my children's voices, I would feel less worried" (ID1).

Another participant stated that,

"I am happy every day when I am able to video chat with my loved ones. They support me and give me motivation every day" (ID3).

Sub-theme 5.2: Psychological support from medical staff

Maximum patients said that the medical staff's care throughout their hospitalization was the most crucial encouraging component, demonstrating that they gave patients a sense of security. One participant stated that,

"I spent a lot of time in the hospital, so the nurses communicated to me a lot" (ID6).

Moreover, stated by another participant,

"Doctors and nurses treated me extremely well and cared for me; I am deeply moved, and I cannot live without their care and support" (ID12).

Sub-theme 5.3: Religious beliefs

The participants' believe in God make them feel more empowered because they know that God is their defender and savior. As stated by one participant,

"I turned exclusively to God. I was aware that even illnesses more severe than Corona could not kill me if he wanted me to survive" (ID4).

For instance, respondent number five stated,

"When I was sick, I could not breathe. God supported me and disregarded my worry. I may have passed away since it was unexpected. Thank God I made it. It's miraculous". (ID5)

Theme 6: Post discharge Concerns and Problems

Sub-theme 6.1: Concerns about one's job

The fear of losing their job was one of the worries of the participants, especially the men.

"One of my major worries throughout the quarantine was the dread of the lack of recovery and incapacity to return to work, which would generate financial troubles for my family" (ID6).

Sub-theme 6.2: Stigmatization of people

The patients' post-discharge worries after returning to society were the final theme. One participant stated that,

"I was frightened for my families, so I didn't want anyone to see. For instance, I was concerned that if the neighbors knew, they might forbid their kids from playing with mine" (ID4).

Sub-theme 6.3: Difficulty to adhere the quarantine standards

Due to the presence of their relatives and their concern about spreading the disease to other family members, one of these patients' issues was adhering to the quarantine requirements after being discharged. One participant stated that,

"It was harder for my kids," I said. For ten days, I was in the hospital, so I wasn't with them" (ID1).

Sub-theme 6.4: Perceptions and acceptance of the people's behavior and attitude.

Some respondents claimed to have embraced the symptoms of their illness and understood how other people felt. One participant stated that,

"I was not offended by their actions, and possibly if I were them, I too would stay away from someone with a COVID- 19. Health concerns are a concern for everyone. I really understood it" (ID5).

7. Discussion

During interviews majority of the participants expressed negation and denial when showing clinical symptoms such as cough with fever and stated that it might be a cold and it cannot be COVID-19. Some participants considered as a sore throat as they believed that the fragrance of various drugs hurts their throat. Therefore, they did not take it seriously and found it hard to accept that they have the corona illness. Similar findings were obtained from a previous study majority of the participants said they attempted to deny and rejected their initial symptoms and were unable to believe that they can have corona. Due to such denial they experimented with self-medication and delaying visits to medical facilities, which aggravated the illness and forced them into the hospital (Student et al., 2021).

The social support of the hospital staff may create the environment for the satisfaction of this fundamental need due to the physical absence of the patient's family members and their lack of presence in the hospital, both of which can obstruct the patient's basic need for communication in the stressful condition of the disease (Rahmatinejad et al., 2020).

The findings are in line with earlier research that shown that people with chronic respiratory diseases like COVID-19 frequently experience anxiety, despair, and terror as among of the disease's many symptoms (Shahyad and Mohammadi, 2020).

These findings are in line with the research of Ali pour et al., which named psychological torture as one of the primary problems with COVID-19 psychosocial challenges and worries (Alipour et al., 2020). The findings of multiple research on COVID patients in China throughout the disease's growth showed that these patients had a high prevalence of certain psychological illnesses, including anxiety, fear, sadness, mood swings, sleeplessness, and post-traumatic stress disorders (Yang et al., 2020) (Liu et al., 2020).

Moreover the vast majority of participants in this current were found to have a dread of dying as evidenced by the statement of the participants. Death was the first thing that comes to their mind. Majority of the participants in the study were feeling like they cannot live anymore and that's why they were too much afraid of death. Similar earlier research was done on the feeling of death anxiety in COVID patients who reported the experience (Rahmatinejad et al., 2020).

The findings of a previous study showed that a number of variables, particularly spiritual experiences, religious beliefs affect patients' perspectives on the illness and attitudes toward it during the stages of diagnosis, treatment, and hospitalization, as well as the degree of adjustment to the disease conditions. Spiritual and religious experiences can help people

cope with their circumstances and find purpose in their lives. They can help patients cope with the disease's unpleasant side effects (Student et al., 2021).

Regarding this, the results of a previous study revealed that anxiety over the decline in household income and financial resources was the most prevalent mental issue in China after the country recovered from SARS. As a result, this component was identified as the key indicator of poor mental health (Shahyad and Mohammadi, 2020).

According to previous study findings, COVID-19-related social stigma also contributed to extra psychological stressors and social hurdles. Stigma can prevent people from getting medical attention and frequently causes delays in disease diagnosis and treatment (Jamili et al., 2022).

8. Conclusion

The above discussions can be concluded that patients' psychological experiences during the COVID-19 crisis were complicated, involving COVID-19-related mental distress symptoms, expectations for their post-discharge lives, and attempts to make sense of their experiences. Stress on the body and mind is present in COVID-19 patients. Their views about the illness gradually changed, and depending on the stage of therapy, so did their emotional reactions, while they were under quarantine. Initial stage patients' unpleasant feelings progressively gave way to a mix of both good and bad feelings. Early psychological remedies can protect people from harm's way and help them develop healthy attitudes and emotions. Positive aspects of our culture may have an impact on things like psychological acclimatization, epidemic prevention, and adequate social support. The majority of the patients vigorously steered their disease-induced self-growth in order to facilitate both short- and long-term physical and emotional recovery.

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